

Development of the Risks from the design of the E-LAND solution to the implementation for the first users

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The E-LAND project is developing a set of tools to allow renewable energy actors to minimize their energy production and consumption costs. The solution computes an optimal scheduler based on user's data (e.g., consumption and production capacities or infrastructures) and external parameters (as forecast or market price). Yet the introduction of this new solution in existing infrastructures force to adopt new protocols that also introduce new risks with the new functionalities. For example, with the E-LAND solution, the future users have to adapt their production from locally stored data to non-local data. The project which started in 2019 now has reached the implementation phase of the tools at the different pilot sites. This paper compares how risks were understood at the beginning of the project, how the risks have developed through the project and how the pilot sites handle their ownership of the risks. This includes the difficulties of physical interaction with the partners and third parties' operators through the pandemic. The paper also evaluates the risk process so far: if the risks foreseen for the pilot sites were accurate, what preparation was necessary for them to understand and handle the risk, and how were the risks communicated through the project? For us having the role as risk manager, our focus on risk awareness and risk communication received good feedbacks from the partners. On the other hand, not foreseen risks arised along the project.

Keywords: E-LAND, risk management, risk mitigations, risk communication, smart grid, energy islands, risk communication.

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